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Internationalisation and complexity: dialogues for diversity or eradicating difference?

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ABSTRACT

The concepts of internationalisation and transnational education (TNE) within Higher Education are ubiquitous phenomena for twenty-first century education. In a globalised context, this can take the form of international students and staff, internationally-delivered programmes, and internationalised content.

Drawing from experiences of working within the busy, diverse, and globally-recognised Birmingham Centre for Railway Research and Education (BCRRE), this paper explores internationalisation in engineering education. Using the themes of diversity and complexity, it considers how these intersect in teaching and learning, particularly in regards programme design and delivery.

The paper takes two case studies: a UK-delivered programme with a diverse student cohort and an internationally-delivered collaborative, transnational programme with an industry partner. Both programmes are taught by staff in one centre within a UK university and both utilise similar teaching, learning, and assessment methods. The two programmes are compared in relation to markers of internationalisation, diversity, and complexity, as well as programme design.

The data highlight not only differing levels of diversity and complexity, but also a need to adjust these faced with different contexts and examples of internationalisation. It is argued, as a result, that there is a need for ongoing, developed examination of levels of diversity and complexity for enhanced internationalisation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Internationalisation represents a key aspect within contemporary higher education, reflecting the need for fit-for-purpose teaching and learning opportunities within a globalised world. As a concept, internationalisation centres upon 'preparing graduates to live in and contribute responsibly to a globally interconnected society' (Higher Education Academy, 2016). This is achieved through a holistic focus encompassing all aspects of teaching and learning, including students, programmes, institutions,

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partnerships, and beyond. Internationalisation thus refers to the integration of home and international students, staff and associates, of global projects, partnerships, and perspectives, and of de-centred, varied, and complex ways of thinking and working in research, teaching, and learning for the twenty-first century. Diversity and complexity as issues are thus of central importance within internationalised education at all levels.

1.1 Scope

This paper considers these issues of diversity and complexity within the context of internationalisation for higher education. Drawing from work and experiences within Birmingham Centre for Railway Research and Education (BCRRE), based at the University of Birmingham (UK), it explores postgraduate taught programmes in railway engineering offered in the UK and overseas. This context has been chosen due to a focus on internationalisation within the centre, primarily evident through the global reach of staff, students, projects, partnerships, and reputation. As a significant research and education centre such global spread offers key experiences of lived diversity as well as the resultant complexities faced by a large working group.

The subject matter of railway engineering, additionally contributes to the complexities under consideration. Railway engineering represents a substantial broad field of study encompassing civil, mechanical, systems, electrical and electronic engineering, as well as materials sciences, physics, design, business studies, sociology, human geography, ergonomics, and economics. Railways as a system of systems, too, are profoundly marked by complexity through dispersion, diversity, variability, and interdependence of internal and external factors.

1.2 Aims and Objectives

This paper's central aim is to explore how higher education internationalisation is and can be informed by diversity and complexity. These matters are considered through the following objectives:

- to determine markers for diversity and complexity within higher education programmes;
- to chart these markers across two programmes, one delivered as a standard UK postgraduate programme, and one as a transnational programmes delivered via flying faculty overseas;
- to compare design and delivery of teaching, learning, and assessment across the two programmes.

By considering these aspects, questions of diversity and complexity within higher education internationalisation are raised in order to promote further examinations of teaching and learning, and assessment for twenty-first century engineering education.

1.3 Method

Two contrasting postgraduate programmes, both offered by BCRRE, University of Birmingham, have been chosen: 'Railways Systems Engineering and Integration', available as a PGCert, PGDip, or MSc on a full- or part-time basis in Birmingham; and 'Urban Railway Engineering', currently available as a PGCert based within Singapore. These two programmes have been selected in order to examine the measures that have been taken and could or should be taken in the future to engage with diversity and complexity in the context of internationalisation.

The programmes are compared in relation to programme design. This has been chosen to account for the complexities at play in examining educational programmes. Programme design includes structure and modules, teaching and learning methods, and assessment patterns, as well as learning outcomes. These are compared through the concept of constructive alignment to inform analysis. Contextual factors impacting design, such as programme team, university regulations, programme age, are also identified and taken into consideration due to how these inform programmes and the notions of diversity and complexity. Programme designs are then mapped against diversity and complexity factors for effective comparison. This comparative analysis proposes the need for profound consideration of diversity and complexity in internationalisation and argues the need for variety both between and within programmes to allow for effective learning opportunities.

1.4 Outline

The paper introduces the contexts under consideration through a background section introducing the case study programmes in more detail. A literature review is then presented to outline the pedagogical concerns relating to diversity, complexity, and internationalisation. The main body considers the case study programmes in relation to the concepts of internationalisation, diversity, and complexity. It then explores the various factors relating to programme design. The findings are discussed to propose the need for enhanced consideration of diversity and complexity in the context of internationalisation for effective learning. Recommendations and future research are provided alongside concluding remarks.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 The University of Birmingham

The University of Birmingham (UoB) is a Russell Group institution defined by its research focus. It was established in 1900 as a ‘civic university’ in the heart of the UK’s second city, Birmingham. It boasts a student population of over 34,000, including 7,875 international students. UoB additionally has a commitment to internationalisation and transnational education through its recently established branch campus in Dubai, UAE.

The faculties of the university are divided into 5 colleges: Arts and Law; Social Sciences; Medical and Dental; Life Sciences; and Engineering and Physical Sciences (EPS). In terms of student population size, EPS, is the third largest, with a study body of 6,656; however, this includes a large international population, making it the second largest of the university, with 1,932 international students. Almost 30% of the college’s students are international, in comparison with 23% of the university’s student population overall. Each college contains a number of Schools grouping together similar subject areas, and each School contains departments and centres. In this structure, BCRRE sits within the School of Engineering.

2.2 Birmingham Centre for Railway Research and Education

BCRRE is a large research and education centre specialising in railway systems with 50 years’ experience. With over 130 members of staff and over 500 students, it is the largest railway research and education centre in Europe. BCRRE has three sections: professional and commercial services; research; and education.

Internationalisation is a central focus for BCRRE with research projects, educational programmes, and partnerships across the globe. The student and staff cohort is

especially representative of such internationalisation: current postgraduate students come from Singapore, Australia, Hong Kong, Thailand, Malaysia, China, South Korea, Switzerland, Portugal, Brazil, Germany, France, USA, India, Belgium, Liberia, Syria, Egypt, Nigeria, Ghana, Iran, and more. Educational programmes in particular engender this internationalisation as students can complete postgraduate study on a full-time, part-time, distance learning international, or transnational basis, see *Table 1*. BCRRE education programmes.

Table 1. BCRRE education programmes

Programme	Study modes
Civil Engineering with Railways	BEng / MEng full-time
Electrical Engineering with Railways	BEng / MEng full-time
Railway Systems Engineering and Integration	PGCert / PGDip / MSc full-time, part-time, distance learning by attending for three week periods
Railway Safety and Control Systems	PGCert / PGDip / MSc full-time, part-time, distance learning by attending for three week periods
Railway Systems Integration	MRes full-time, part-time
Urban Railway Engineering	PGCert part-time transnational

2.3 Railway Systems Engineering and Integration

The postgraduate programmes in Railway Systems Engineering and Integration (RSEI) are the longest-running educational programmes in BCRRE. After being first offered at the University of Sheffield, the programmes were established at the University of Birmingham in 2005. Initially designed based on British Rail graduate programmes for entry into the rail sector, the programme is a global success story bolstered by exemplary reputation.

The full MSc programme covers 120 taught credits and 60 research credits. The modules encompass technical topics of control systems, rolling stock, infrastructure, and traction and non-technical subjects of railway operations, ergonomics, economics and business management, and systems engineering and integration.

Each year typically sees 25 students begin the programme full-time, and up to 40 students commencing part-time study. As a result, there are normally upwards of 100 students registered on the programme at any one time. Some 35 students graduate with an MSc each academic year.

Students enrol on the programme with two main levels of experience. Firstly, those with no or limited experience in the rail sector use the programme to start a career in rail, including those having just completed undergraduate study in engineering and those changing career. Secondly, those with experience in one aspect of the rail sector use the programme as a stepping stone to career progression, often leading to chartership and more senior-level positions.

2.4 Urban Railway Engineering

Urban Railway Engineering was recently established in 2016. It is a postgraduate collaborative programme between BCRRE and SMRT, one of the two metro operators in Singapore. The programme emerged from a successful research partnership between the two institutions. Faced with aging assets and workforce, as well as growing population and demands on the network, SMRT sought to professionalise their staff, choosing to work with BCRRE to develop a certified postgraduate programme.

The PGCert programme comprises 60 taught credits across modules covering technical and non-technical subjects. All students complete compulsory modules on railway management, basic railway technologies, asset management, and railway contexts, which covers topics such as ergonomics, economics, and operations. In addition, students take two optional modules focusing on the technical area in which they hold their day jobs, out of command and control systems, infrastructure, rolling stock, and traction and power.

The programme is predominantly designed for members of SMRT staff undertaking the company's graduate programmes as engineers. Additionally, operations staff take the first year modules. To date, a range of existing more experienced staff have also elected to study for enhanced knowledge and expertise. This has seen upwards of 80 students commence study each year.

Several key types of students enrol on the programme: developing engineers, operations staff, and experienced staff. The programme serves to develop depth of competencies within one area of railway engineering and is complemented through enhanced breadth across railway engineering technical and non-technical expertise. The programme additionally contributes to development of staff working towards professional chartership with the Institute of Engineers Singapore (IES).

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Internationalisation

As aforementioned, internationalisation is used to refer to the need to prepare students to work in globalised contexts for the twenty-first century. This encompasses student and staff engagement, subject matter taught, methods for teaching and developing students' skills and competencies, university partnerships, and beyond. For the purpose of this paper, internationalisation is defined by students, staff, and studies, all of which are considered in the following discussion.

One component within internationalisation is transnational education. This is defined as 'the provision of a higher education degree programme leading to a [...] qualification for students based in a country other than the one in which the awarding institution is located' (HEGlobal, 2016). Transnational education encompasses distance and online learning, collaborative provision with partnerships, and physical delivery overseas through branch campuses or flying faculty. Globally, the two leading national economies within transnational education are Australia and the United Kingdom (Clark, 2012). Within the UK, transnational education accounts for a significant percentage of international students and higher education institution strategies: according to Universities UK International during the academic year 2015-2016 there were 701,010 students on UK HE TNE programmes, more than the number of international students studying in the UK, alongside 82% of UK universities delivering transnational education (2018: 2) operating in all but 15 countries worldwide. Programmes cover all levels, subjects, and means of study, with student numbers growing by 17% between 2012-2013 and 2015-2016 (HEGlobal, 2016). Transnational education consequently is a significant area of growth and development within Higher Education; this is of particular importance in the present paper, given the inclusion of a transnational programme.

3.2 Diversity

The question of diversity within higher education is a long-standing subject of research and consideration. Typically associated with equality and inclusion, diversity can be said to refer to “an approach that values difference and treats each individual fairly and with dignity and respect, free from harassment and bullying” (Universities UK, 2019). This is often linked to protected characteristics and the ramifications of the 2010 Equality Act. In the context of higher education, this entails valuing and integrating difference within staff and student populations, as well as across curricula.

Considering the broad issue of equality and diversity in learning and teaching in higher education, the Equality Challenge Unit, addresses diversity with reference to matters of belonging, partnership, and embedding equality. As highlighted, this includes a focus on pedagogised norms and pedagogised others (Equality Challenge Unit, 2016) as central concerns for diversity. Similarly, Coleman identifies the importance of examining the what, who, how, and where of diversity within higher education (2015). However, diversity is, he argues, a “dirty word” due to its eradication and obfuscation of difference, value, and definition (2015).

In the context of the engineering sector, across both industry and academia, diversity poses a further concern. In their work on diversity, Royal Academy of Engineering highlight the striking statistics that 92% of engineers are male and 94% are white (2016). RAEng’s Diversity Programme assesses the status of diversity and equality across the sector, proposes methods for improving equality and diversity, and seeks to lead the way in diversity (2016). The work produced by this group includes suggested toolkits for enhancing diversity, which begin by defining inclusion with reference to all people; the cultures, environments, and processes of an organisation; how all people feel; and an ongoing commitment and effort towards inclusion (Royal Academy of Engineering, 2015). Diversity, as the consequence of inclusion efforts, cannot be a coincidence.

Drawing from the research, the following markers for considering diversity have been identified:

- What: encompassing subject matter;
- Who: covering staff, students, and partners across gender, age, sexuality, ethnicity, religion, disability, cultural background, socio-economic class, education;
- Where: referring to spaces and places of teaching and learning opportunities;
- How: involving pedagogic practice, including normative and marginalised practices, and inclusive practice.

These are used to explore the case study programmes in the following discussion.

3.3 Complexity

Complexities are about non-linearity, indeterminism, and variety. The study of this in relation to natural sciences has been determined complexity theory, and focuses on bifurcations. Applicable to physics, mathematics, biology, and chemistry, complexity theory also holds a key role within social sciences as a way to examine organisations and social structures. For Osberg and Biesta, complexity theory goes “beyond” binaries to propose new methods for consideration (2010).

As an area of study, complexity theory has additionally been used as a lens to explore education. Kauko further considers this in the context of higher education, arguing that

complexity is ‘the basic condition of higher education systems’ (2014). In their edited volume, Osberg and Biesta highlight how complexity theory allows for examination of both the promotion of complexity in and through education and the reduction of complexity in and through education (2010). Both matters are, they argue, a form of political intervention (Ibid.).

At its heart, complexity theory concerns valuing complexity. This seems to suggest a need for the simultaneous promotion of complexities and of new, albeit variant, orders, both engaging with the very concept of complexity itself. This theoretical positioning is used to guide the ensuing discussion.

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Internationalisation, Diversity, and Complexity markers

Both programmes can be considered forms of international higher education due to student cohort, staff, and study options, as shown in *Table 2*. Internationalisation markers. International students, well integrated across both programmes, are defined as those from outside the UK and Europe, following the University’s definition for fees. Similarly, international staff are those not born and raised within the UK.

Regarding study options for markers of internationalisation, this covers patterns, topics, and methods for study. Patterns refer to part- and full-time study options, with internationalised study patterns encompassing ways of studying that allow students to join the programme and participate from a context outside the UK. This is available in the form of part-time study for both programmes, with RSEI comprising short periods of stay in the UK and URE, transnational classroom-based study in Singapore. Internationalised study topics draws from the literature to refer to the inclusion of a range of topics, contexts, theories, and approaches encompassed within teaching materials. In the context of railway education, this covers studying different technologies and their adoptions across a range of global, historical, and technical contexts and examples, as well as differing tools, companies, and business models. Similarly, methodologies concerns teaching and learning approaches designed to get students to engage with new and different ways of thinking and being. This includes group work with people of different backgrounds and experience, activities focused on critical thinking and analysis, open-ended questions where there is no single right answer.

Table 2. Internationalisation markers

Internationalisation components	Railway Systems Engineering and Integration	Urban Railway Engineering
International students	X	X
International staff	X	X
International study patterns	X	X
International study topics	X	X
Internationalised study methodologies	X	X

The identification indicated within the table shows both programmes have the same levels of internationalisation. However, further comment is required to highlight the

nuanced at play. Whilst all aspects of internationalisation are present, this is at different levels, which can be unpacked further in relation to diversity.

Regarding diversity markers, the programmes show differing levels of diversity, as highlighted in *Table 3*. Diversity markers. All data are taken from academic year 2017-2018 with details regarding what, who, how, and where provided. Students refer to those registered on the programme and staff covers module leaders and any teaching fellows playing a substantial role in delivery and assessment of module.

Table 3. Diversity markers

	Railway Systems Engineering and Integration	Urban Railway Engineering
What	Technical and non-technical subjects covering global perspectives across range of businesses and backgrounds.	Technical and non-technical subjects covering some range of perspectives.
Who	Students male and female of a range of ages, ethnicities, educational backgrounds, career paths. Staff (n=8): majority white males (n=6), with some ethnicity and gender variation	Students predominantly male, university educated, majority of Chinese heritage working in engineering, of a range of ages. Staff (n=16): majority white males (n=9), with range of ethnicities and genders
How	Teaching delivery 9-5 lecture-based, with evening activities until 7:30. Delivery by academic staff and a broad range of guest lecturers.	Teaching delivery 8:30-5:30 mixture of lecture and activities. Delivery by academic staff.
Where	Monday-Friday 5-day Birmingham-based modules in accessible rooms with movable furniture, with further work completed independently.	Saturday-Wednesday 5-day Singapore-based modules in very large accessible rooms with majority movable furniture, taught over weekends at the request of the partner, with further work completed independently.

The diversity markers indicate differing levels across the programmes. URE demonstrates reduced diversity in terms of ‘what’, ‘who’ (students), ‘how’, and ‘where’. This suggests the transnational programme lends itself to less diversity. For URE this is especially influenced by the collaborative nature of the programme with one company, leading to specific demands regarding content (‘what’) and when teaching modules can occur (‘where’). The diversity of ‘who’ is also impacted by company demographics. In terms of methods (‘how’), the reduced timeframe for teaching hours actually signals enhanced equality and inclusivity for students not having to attend during evenings (though this is mitigated by weekend teaching). Moreover, for many students on RSEI, part-time study requires staying in Birmingham for one week, not just away from work, but also from family, friends, and homes. In this respect, the part-time model that allows commuting due to the Singapore-context of URE is favourable, albeit informed by contextual factors.

Intriguingly, the core teaching team within URE represents increased diversity, which additionally intersects with internationalisation of the programme. This is in part motivated by the intensive nature of teaching for URE, which requires all 6 modules to be taught in parallel to the different student groups due to staff and student availability and thus necessitates a larger teaching team comprised of more colleagues across

the wider BCRRE group. Additionally, the Birmingham-based RSEI utilises a high level of guest lecturers travelling from UK contexts, which is clearly impractical for a Singapore programme.² The transnational nature of URE therefore has substantial interplay with diversity markers that might be both examined further and mitigated through the notion of complexity.

For the purpose of this paper, the application of complexity theory to higher education serves as an analytical lens through which to consider difference and diversity in the context of internationalisation. If complexity concerns bifurcation and non-linearity as its essence, using complexity theory to assess the case study programmes provides a means for considering options, decentralisation, and new orders. As a line of enquiry, this highlights the politics of educational practice.

Taking bifurcation as a marker of complexity, the case study programmes promote complexity in the following manners:

- Study pathways
- Leaver destinations
- Study impetus
- Programme content

These aspects can be loosely divided into those concerning the student (pathways, destinations, and impetus) and the programme (content). Regarding the former, the presence of a range of pathways, destinations, and reasons for study not only increase complexity for the student, but also require further diversity and complexity across the programme. This is all strongly present across RSEI, demonstrating high levels of complexity. By contrast, the bespoke collaborative nature of URE limits complexity at the student level and thus requires further complexity at programme level in order to address this.

4.2 Programme Design

Markers of internationalisation, diversity, and complexity are a starting point for comparison. More detailed examination is available by considering programme design, as shown in *Table 4*. Programme design.

Table 4. Programme design

	Railway Systems Engineering and Integration	Urban Railway Engineering
Taught Modules	8x 10-credit 2x 20-credit	6x 10-credit
Teaching hours	5-day intensive with evening activities	5-day intensive
Teaching location	Birmingham	Singapore
Assessment	Class test, written assignment, and final exam all submitted online	Written assignment and/or final exam all submitted online

² In some cases guest lectures have been provided via video, however, this has not been used extensively in favour of delivery by those physically present.

Further notes		Compulsory for graduate engineers in SMRT
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Programme design is limited by a number of external factors, such as the modular system of higher education and the requirement for 60 credits at PGCert level. The University of Birmingham uses 10- and 20-credit modules, additionally limiting programme design. Furthermore, the aforementioned markers of internationalisation, diversity, and complexity are built into programme design. For instance, modules delivered intensively through one week, rather than across a semester, offer more compact teaching and learning that promotes part-time study, particularly for individuals from a range of locations.

5. DISCUSSION

The data presented above highlight similarities across the two programmes. Internationalisation, diversity, and complexity markers appear throughout the case studies and the programme designs reflect consistency of pedagogical approach. At a surface level, therefore, these serve as examples of how diversity and complexity can be integrated within the context of higher education internationalisation. More broadly, the programme design also provides a demonstration of how a UK-based programme might be transposed into a different context for transnational education as part of an internationalisation strategy.

Behind this initial similarity, however, the programmes espouse difference and variety, and indicate some key concerns. The focus on diversity and complexity markers demonstrate this. Regarding diversity, the URE programme is shown to offer a smaller range of diversity across all markers, with the exception of module staff. Similarly, markers indicate limited complexity within URE. Although these aspects are likely influenced by the age, development, and bespoke nature of the programme. These results call for increased consideration of internationalisation.

Considering these factors of diversity and complexity in parallel demonstrates how different aspects of a programme could be adjusted for enhanced internationalisation. For example, reduced complexity of student factors might result in a need for developed complexity of materials and content to allow a programme to better meet the needs of internationalisation. Adjusting teaching methodologies or study patterns can therefore be prompted through analysis of the diversity/complexity markers. This suggests that such analysis can serve as a pedagogical tool for enhancing internationalisation.

Using diversity and complexity to consider URE as an example of transnational education in the context of internationalisation underscores some of the limitations around TNE as an internationalisation strategy. The data show that for the case of URE, diversity, complexity, and even internationalisation are more limited than within RSEI. Transnationalism is thus not necessarily equivalent to enhanced internationalisation. Although this result is likely influenced by limited experience within transnationalism and by the specificities of the case study programme under consideration, it is still significant to note such reductions in diversity and complexity.

This highlights a broader issue with focusing on internationalisation as a unique and coherent aspect within higher education. Indeed, this analysis emphasises the need for encompassing the ‘what’, ‘who’, ‘how’, and ‘where’ of diversity; the bifurcation

possibilities of complexity; and the student, staff, and study options of internationalisation, suggesting that no one aspect can be taken in isolation.

Complexity theory particularly attends to these matters, inviting consideration of bifurcation. To return to the work of Osberg and Biesta (2010), there is a need to address the politics of complexity, in terms of both promotion and reduction. In the context of internationalisation, complexities can enhance this. Complexities can offer means for highlighting and celebrating difference as an integral part of internationalisation. They can also provide means for managing problematics of internationalisation regarding diversity. Finally, complexities put forward approaches for new persuasive pedagogies across various internationalised contexts.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper has examined the concepts of diversity and complexity within higher education internationalisation. It has taken two case study programmes, both demonstrating examples of internationalisation, and compared markers of internationalisation, diversity, and complexity, alongside programme design. It contends that, whilst programmes can appear similar on the surface, exploration of diversity and complexity invites more detailed examination of internationalisation. It uses the case study programmes to argue the methodological values of diversity and complexity analysis for pedagogy. Indeed, as demonstrated above, the presence of individual markers is not sufficient to suggest developed internationalisation. Instead, a combination of factors concerning diversity and complexity must be taken into consideration and explored in conjunction for enhanced internationalisation of higher education.

It is suggested that future study would be enhanced by a broader examination taking into consideration attainment and student and staff evaluation in order to further explore effectiveness and successes of teaching and learning within internationalisation. Such study/ies might consider programme results, alongside qualitative student evaluations and staff reflections. This range of data would allow for a more enhanced examination of diversity and complexity within internationalisation. Regardless of future analysis, internationalisation – both as context and as approach – should continue to be subject to close and careful scrutiny for educational practice.

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